

The Design of Local Wisdom Learning for Providing Creative Activities for Juveniles with Exhibit Media: Suan-Oui Youth Center

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Abstract : This paper studied the application of the design of local wisdom learning for providing creative activity for juveniles with exhibit media. The Suan-oui Youth Center has the objectives to design and develop exhibit media that encourage participation and learning of youths on local wisdom of Ratanakosin Island. The research was conducted in three stages: 1) to study the principle of local wisdom learning of cultural heritage at Ratanakosin Island 2) to study exhibit media that encouraged participation and creative activities of youth on local wisdom learning, and 3) to design a youth center that provide media exhibition for local wisdom learning. The research revealed the following: 34.6 percent of respondents wanted to apply local living wisdom in their career and for hobby. At least two kinds of exhibit media effectively provided creative activities for youths. A multi-purpose area, for example, with still pictures, visual symbols, and simulations would increase the level of youths' interaction and participation.

Keywords : exhibit media, local wisdom, youth center, design

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